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Editor

Dr. Kamlesh Kumar Singh

Assistant Professor

Gaya Prasad Smarak Govt. P.G. College
Azamgarh

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Historical Prospective of Mandal Commission and Evaluation of Social Changes

Amit Kumar Yashpal*

The one of the most controversial issue of 1990s was implementation of the Mandal commission recommendations. There was policy of providing reservations in central government jobs to backward castes. Although it was adopted to ensure upward the deprived sections of the society, it definitely helped some certain groups but there was also a group who were economically very poor but they were not given reservations. Narshima Rao announced for giving additional 10% reservations to poors among the forward castes but it was neglected by the Supreme Court.

In India, the concept of inequality is historically and culturally different from other places. Andre Beteille regarding inequality in Indian rural context explained “societies were divided into groups and categories and in this traditional system these inequalities were closely related to the inequalities of castes.” Thus, in Indian society or Hindu culture, the caste system is the basis of social structure. Here group entity dominates individual entity. Also, here position of an individual cannot be separated from his Jati which he belong to. Initially, Indian society was divided into four social classes with particular functions. In these four varnas, the conditions of the sudras were very difficult and their duty was to serve the three higher classes. A sharp distinction was made between the three higher classes and sudras. Later the stratification of Indian society became more rigid such as marraiges were permitted only within the same groups, commensality etc were practiced. And in the differentiation of the society conditions of lower castes became worst. In the later period the percentage of these castes in government jobs according to their proportion remained low and it was found in Mandal report 1980, the population of OBCs were 52% of total population but had access only 12.55% government jobs and only 04.69% of class I jobs. The government of India appointed First Backward Class commission in 1953, but their recommendations were not accepted.

The Mandal Commission Report 1980

Bindheshwari Prasad Mandal commonly known as B.P.Mandal was born in yadav family in Banaras on Aug. 25, 1918 but he was from Madhepura, Bihar. He was the former Chief Minister of Bihar in 1968 for 30 days, he was a member of parliament in Lok Sabha from 1967-70 and 1977-79. He was the chairman appointed for the second backward classes commission by the Prime Minister Shri Morarji Desai announced on Dec. 20, 1978 during the rule of Janta Party government. The commission was formed on Jan. 01, 1979. The composition of this commission were as:-

- a) B.P. Mandal (Ex-MP) - Chairman
- b) R.R. Bhole, M.P. - Member
- c) S.S. Gill - Secretary
- d) L.R. Naik (Ex-MP) - Member
- e) K. Subramaniam - Member
- f) Dewan Mohanlal - Member

The commission was termed to determine the criteria for socially and educationally backward classes, to examine the desirability of making provisions for the reservations of appointments or posts to such backward classes and to recommend steps for their advancement and also present their report to the President.

As the first backward class commission was rejected, this time the commission wanted to work properly for classification of backward classes and they also used objective tests and they

* U.G.C.-JRF, P.G. Student, Department of History, Faculty of Social Sciences, Banaras Hindu University

issued three questionnaires to all the state governments, central ministers and general public in April, 1979. Here they are requested to supply information about the steps taken for the welfare of OBCs, their representation in government services and social status of the manual workers, incidence of drop-outs etc. The all 30 ministries, departments and 31 attached and sub-ordinate offices furnished the desired information. This questionnaires were also published in leading English and Vernacular presses of each states during the commission's tour. The replies of all questionnaires were given to the commission.

The commission toured across the whole country to get information about the conditions and the problems of socially and educationally backward communities. They visited 84 district headquarters, 37 villages, attended 171 formal meetings and received 2638 representations from public and voluntary organisations. After that they constituted a panel of 25 experts to survey the socio-educational field of the country under Prof. M.N. Srinivas. They collected data on the basis of 1891 and 1931 census and then that was framed to link the traditional occupation with caste. After 1931, the listing of castes was discontinued in the later census. They also lead legal and constitutional issues and judgements given by the apex court and various high courts relating to the reservations or other benefits provided by several states. After all that exercises, the commission gave 11 criterias for determining social and educational backwardness including economic conditions also. These criterias were grouped in social, educational and economical. In these parameters social factors were given 3 points, educational had 2 points and economical had 1 points for determining backwardness of a class. In this way, total scores of these parameters were 22 and the groups who scored 11 points and above were considered as backward. They recommended 27% reservations for OBCs as their was already 22.5% reservations for SC/ST and total quantum of reservation should not exceed 50% according to the article 15(4) and 16(4) of the constitution. The commission proposed the schemes of reservations for OBCs were as:-

- i) Candidates belonging to OBCs recruited on the basis of merit in an open competition should not adjusted against their reservation of 27%.
- ii) Reservation should also apply in promotions.
- iii) Reserved quota remained vacant for 3 Years and deserved thereafter.
- iv) Relaxation of age should be extended to OBCs.
- v) A roster system should be adopted by the concerned authorities for each categories.

The above recommendations should be applicable in central and state government, nationalized banks and private sectors that received any financial assistance from the government. Several financial assistance should be given to the OBCs, who obtained special vocational training, to setup small scale industries on their own. The commission strongly recommended to implement progressive land legislation so that it effects basic structure changes in the existing production relations in the countryside, this would be proved as a better step for the welfare and upliftment backward classes as top peasantry always have dominance over them. Also a part of surplus land become available as a result of the operation of land ceiling loans etc and that should be allotted poor landless labours of OBCs they also recommended to include certain occupational communities like fishermen, banjaras etc in the OBC list as they also suffered from untouchability in some parts of the country. Some backward sections like Gaddis in Himachal Pradesh, fishermen in coastal areas etc were recommended the areas of their concentratrion should be covered out into separate constituencies.

The commission submitted its report on Dec. 30, 1980 to the president Giani Zail Singh.

Implementations and Agitations -

The report of Mandal commission was submitted on Dec. 1980 but after that no action was taken on it and it was further placed in cold storage till the next ten years. It was setup by Janta Party government. In 1980, the general election held and Indira Gandhi had won the election with immense majority. She neither absolutely rejected Mandal commission, not took any step for it. Later, Rajiv Gandhi, also did not touch it.

Now after ten years of the submission of report the National Front in its election manifesto 1989 supports reservations for backward classes and they offered to implement it hastily. V.P. Singh became the Prime Minister of India on Dec. 02, 1989. And his intention about the Mandal commission reflected in the President's address to the joint session of both houses of parliament on Dec. 20, 1989. President R.Venkataraman said that the government will take appropriate steps to implement the recommendations of Mandal commission. Then V.P. Singh on Aug. 07, 1989 stunned the entire nation by announcing the acceptance of the some recommendations of Mandal commission and enforced 27% reservations in central government jobs and its public undertaking for OBCs.

V.P. Singh calculated that he would be considered as a champion of backward communities after its implementation and this also solves the issue of Devi Lal and others. He admitted that several MLAs of Janta Dal insisted him to implement it and he always denied that the decision was taken suddenly because of any political reason, but he always wanted to improve the condition of backwards.

But a lot of questions arised before V.P. Singh as would only the reservations in central government jobs genuinely bring up the oppressed section of society? What about those who were belonged to economically poorer sections and did not placed in any category? And did the reservations in various post in state government either helped the backward classes or the exploitation reduced in other way?

There was also a lot of confusions regarding the identification of OBCs by the commission. The inclusion of some castes in OBCs whose social and educational backwardness is not self-evident and their claimed to be economically backward arise doubt. Some of them as vokkaligas in Karnataka etc also there was seen some confusion in the OBC list as Jats were treated as OBC for Ajmer in Rajasthan not else anywhere. Dhobi placed as OBC in Uttar Pradesh but not in Bihar etc, this all created some complications and mistrust on Mandal report. It is noted that the commission had used the census of 1931 for caste-wise enumeration of population. But V.P. Singh did not want to listen any argue and wanted to implement it as soon as possible. And V.P. Singh government's notified about the implementation of 27% reservations to OBCs on Aug. 13, 1990 within one week of the announcement.

It took some time to realize the wide-range effects of the notification and also the reaction came was very threatening. Now there became ideological battle between various groups. Also some groups were firmly opposing the Mandal recommendations and saw it as emergence of perpetual caste war in the society. Now also there were certain groups whose stands on this commission were as- First, those who belonged to twice-born i.e. (higher castes of Hindus), Persian, Christians, etc they strongly opposed the recommendations. Second, some of the twice-born who were in the left Party or others, were supporting Mandal report or remained neutral also as they opposed 'Caste' as a subject to identify backwardness they wanted economic criteria to be introduced also. Third, those who were confused as they could be included in the OBC list but were not listed so they argued for inclusion or oppose it. Fourth, they were Dalits and Adivasis, they strongly supported it, they were aware of it that twice-born were opposing not only the reservations for OBCs. But they were against to any type of reservations, if they succeed then they would next move to suppress the dalits.

Now the notification of its implement frightened the entire country. There were protests occurred against and for it in every parts of the country. The northern Part of the country caught fire into mass upsurge were as there was some minor stir in various southern states the reason was that several demands of backwards sought to be accepted there but were not in northern regions. Now several parts of the country were burnt, a lot of rallies had been transformed into bands and rallies. The administration closed all schools and colleges for a month in Delhi and other regions as a lot of incidents of killing came to be happened. The Delhi transportation corporation also ordered to remove glass panes from all its buses. There also Sharad Yadav and Ramvilas Paswan who continued exorting the backwards to come out on the streets in support of Mandal commission.

As a protest spread various parts its effects also seen in country wide. In Bihar, Laloo Prasad Yadav who stood strongly with Mandal commission and he was very eagerly to implement the recommendations. Though, there was bloodiest anti Mandal protest occurred which took several lives. There were still the traces of feudalism found in Bihar. It was expected to gear up a possible caste war. The upper castes in Bihar were annoyed and formed 'Rashtriya Swarna Mukti Morcha' in Bhumihars dominated Muzafferpur, they demanded a 'Swarna Rajya' in Bihar, U.P., M.P., West Bengal and Haryana.

In Uttar Pradesh, there was the government of Mulayam Singh Yadav. There in U.P., the government had closed all the university and colleges. Government property were harmed, railway lines were broken down. Some students were polishing shoes, pulling rickshaws etc to reflect the outcomes the reservations. But Mulayam Singh Yadav supported the Mandal commission. In Orissa, Biju Pattnaik criticised caste based reservation and had announced not going to implement it. In Punjab, it was announced that the decision of implementation would leave to a popular government as various Akali Dal and militant groups unable to take stand. In Haryana, the Chief Minister Hukum Chautala welcomed the notification and but Haryana also suffered from a lot of violent clashes. Hukum Singh embraced the union government by claiming that jats, ahirs, gujjars, saini were not included in the list. In Himachal Pradesh, the army had to be called in several cities to settle down the clashes. The Chief Minister Shanta Kumar rejected the recommendations and announced to implement 'Antodaya Scheme' to provide benefits to one lakh poor families. The Chimanbhai Patel, Chief Minister, in Gujarat announced that the Mandal commission would not be implemented, this remained the Gujarat peaceful during the reservation riots. The Southern states also remained peaceful only there were some protests as rail and rasta rokos, rallies and bands etc in Andhra Pradesh and others were almost silent.

Self-immolation -

There was a lot of self-immolation incidents took place in several parts of the country against this reservation scheme. More than 65 students of different schools and colleges self-immolated.

A well known case of Rajiv Goswami, 20 years, the student of Deshbandhu College, Delhi University. He was on hunger strike for 9 days but no reaction came out from the government and then he took a terrible step of self-immolation. He later became the face of anti-mandal protest. The other student Surinder Singh Chauhan who also self-immolated in the capital. His dying statement was "it is not a suicide, it is a sacrifice." After that seventeen years old Akhilesh Pandey from Gwalior, Rajiv Gautam a 21 years old post-graduated student from Sirsa, fifteen years old Chetan Gautam, 16 years old Archana Kumari etc committed suicide or self-immolations in several parts of the country. These students considered the notification as a threat to their future jobs. But the main reason behind the unemployment was economic policies of the government since mid 1970s. Many of the students simply went by newspapers headlines etc and they got depressed, frusted and dismayed.

There was a vital role of media in protest and agitations which the country had faced. The electronic media was controlled by government but the non-electronic media like newspapers and other continued published such statements that threatened the students. The Indian Express (New Delhi), a national daily newspaper between the middle of August to first week of October published 2,067 column-centimeters of front page space to the news report of the violence and 3,600 column-centimeters off the front page used for it. Similarly, other newspaper did the same thing. The Times of India stated against reservations that it would perpetuate casteism and it never create a pan-Indian identity. These all scared the students and guardians too. The students in turn, took such steps of self-immolations, suicides, etc.

V.P. Singh government's for implementation of reservations to OBCs has suddenly changed the direction of Indian politics. Now it gave opportunities to political parties to polarize their vote bank. Now every political parties tried to convince that 52% vote bank.

After all that, congress had won the election in 1991 and the government notified to provide additional 10% reservation to poorer among forward castes and second to introduce economic criteria within 27% reservation of OBCs. The addition of 10% reservation increased total reservations more than 50% i.e. 59.9% and it had always been difficult for previous judicial system to give the decision of more than 50% reservation in public employment. Thus the matter then sent to the Supreme Court of India. And also introduction of economic criteria within 27% reservation in OBCs does not have serious political consequences as it was almost not much changes because of their economic conditions.

Supreme Court Judgement

The Supreme Court had put stay order on Sep. 23, 1990 on the notification of V.P. Singh government's decision. The issue was sent to a special nine-judge bench of the Supreme Court to give their decision. The judgement was given in favour of Mandal commission by a majority of six to three on Nov. 16, 1992.

In the memorandum of National Front government on Aug. 13, 1990 it was said that in the first stage the Mandal commission recommendation would not be adopted for armed forces, technology and educational institutions. The congress government had also issued another memorandum on Sep. 25, 1991 with the modification of previous memorandum of 1990 to provide an additional 10% reservation to economically poorer among forward castes and within 27% reservation of OBCs there should be preference given to poorer among them. But it is also noted that the congress had not issued any criteria to distinguish the poorer section of them.

The Supreme Court had rejected Narshima Rao government's notification to introduce economic criteria within 27% reservation in OBCs because the government failed to describe the criteria to distinguish economically poorer or socially advanced group within the OBCs. There had also arisen the issue of caste based reservation. The majority of judgement had supported it. The matter of reservation is not just a Mandal issue stated by the judgement. Mandal commission led down a methodology for implementing reservation for OBC. It was also cleared by the judgement that word Class used in article 16(4) of the constitution was used in sense of social class not in the sense of Marxist terminology and added that caste is nothing but a socially and occupationally homogeneous class.

The Supreme Court has struck down the congress government order of extending 10% reservation as the court had firmed up its earlier decision against exceeding 50% limit of reservation in jobs. The Supreme Court also rejected the arguments that reservation policy would sacrifice merit and impairs efficiency in administration as it was cleared that reservation was not given in technical posts in research organisations, in specialities and super specialities in medicine, post of professor, pilots, scientists and technicians in nuclear and space applications. It was also cleared that benefit of reservation would apply to appointments only not in promotions.

The various political parties also welcomed the judgement of the Supreme Court. The congress had been particularly embarrassed by the apex court as it has struck down their decision of economic criteria in reservations. But later it becomes an agenda in the elections manifesto for parties to gain the vote of higher castes. BJP also did not want loose their Hindu vote bank so they also accepted it. CPI and CPI (M) both has appreciated the judgement but it is noted that CPI (M) supported economic criteria while CPI supported it without any doubt.

The Supreme Court after the judgement suggested the government to identify the Creamy layer and, a committee was formed under the leadership of Ramnandan Prasad, former judge of Patna High Court. The committee submitted its report on March 16, 1993. This committee has formulated some guidelines to identify the Creamy layer.

It is also noted that this was the period in 1992 when the market has opened and a new wave of privatization of economy was promoted. This ruined the reservation provided in public sector. In response of privatization wave, there was also demanded for reservation in private sector. But the MNAs and Indian capitalist had certainly opposed it.

The Mandal issue had finally been resolved by Central Government as they had accepted the recommendations of Prasad's committee for the reservation given on Sep. 08, 1992, it identified Creamy layer. On April 10, 2008 the reservation has also applied in educational institutions for better development of OBCs in this field also.

There was a wide range impact of Mandal commission on the social, political and economic life in the society. The 27% reservation has now provided to backward castes in Central government jobs. Also the states has their own view on the Mandal report. No doubt the caste based reservation has brought a lot of changes to those castes who were generally engaged in their traditional occupations. They were small landholders, tenants, agricultural labour, impoverished village artisans, unskilled worker etc who were now got an opportunity to make their presence in government jobs where their percentage was always very low. This has broken 5000-years old power structure where the only elites and landlords were the center of power. Mandal commission was a primitive step towards Social Justice. No doubt it has reduced social discrimination against backward castes.

Mandal commission has brought an immense political changes in the society. It has increased the political power of plebeians' i.e. common people. The upper caste resistance against reservation aroused indignation among the lower castes and it consolidates the OBC groups. And many OBCs stopped voting for upper caste notables and they preferred to elect representatives from their own communities. It was the impact of Mandal commission that all the Chief Ministers belong to backward castes in Bihar. Later there also has dominance of backward castes in other northern states such as U.P., Madhya Pradesh etc. The Mandal commission report has also included a number of backward Muslim castes along with backward Hindus. This has created a political bond between backward Hindu castes and Muslims after 1990s.

The Mandal commission gave 27% reservation in Central government jobs to OBCs, it definitely raised their economic condition. It strengthened their economic power in administration and politics. Here, the castes were included where the average values of families assets were 25% atleast below the state average.

In this way, Mandal commission proved a turning point for those castes who were always being oppressed and lagged behind the mainstream of the society. There has changes a lot but the main objectives of Mandal commission is still remained to be fulfilled.

Hence, in the last decade of 20th century, a historical decision was taken by the Prime Minister V.P. Singh in 1990 to implement some of the recommendations of Mandal commission report. This has made him 'Messiah' of backward and oppressed section of society. V.P. Singh also had to sacrifice his political carrier for Mandal commission. It is said that the motive behind his decision was to save his government from being collapsed but he always denied this, and argued that it was needed for Social Justice.

It was a challenge before government to bring backwards in mainstream of society and V.P. Singh saw the solution in Mandal commission and provide reservation to them. Hence it is said that reservation has been given to downtrodden and oppressed section of society because of their miserable condition and as also they were neglected for a long time but it is also a fact that the main objectives of Mandal commission is even needed to be fulfilled.

Lastly by the statement of V.P. Singh "the scheme is necessary because it gives the backwards a sense of being part of governance system and compensates for generation of discrimination and also it paves the ground for upward mobility."

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